

A Linguistic Analysis of the Borderscape: Signs of Migration on the French-Italian Border

Alessandra Terranova

University of Edinburgh

Abstract. Linguistic landscapes provide us with a valuable insight into linguistic diversity, language barriers, boundaries, and the link between language use and identity, particularly in politically contested or border areas. This study explores such borderscapes by looking at linguistic signs of migration in two areas of the French-Italian border, along the mountain paths between Ventimiglia and Menton and between Clavière and Briançon. The primary data source is Luca Prestia's photography project 'Beyond the border. Migration and multilingual signs at European borderscapes' (Prestia and Faloppa, 2022), supplemented by sources such as activist media, online newspapers, and street-level images captured on Google Street View. I will analyse the signs both quantitatively and qualitatively, following the taxonomy proposed by Spolsky and Cooper (1991). Moreover, by applying Scollon and Scollon's (2003) Geosemiotics framework, this project aims to go beyond quantifying the number of languages: signs can only be understood when related to their placement in a social and cultural context. The signs come from a variety of sources such as activists, migrants, and organisations, and are directed towards multiple viewers: the people migrating, the authorities limiting their freedom of movement, the drivers along the roads they cross, and the wider society they interact with. By applying a precise framework such as the one introduced by Scollon & Scollon (2003) may lend us a new way to look at these borders and at the multiple human and social dynamics shaping their Linguistic Landscape, where multilingualism is a possible mean to overcome cultural boundaries.

Keywords: semiotics; sociolinguistics; linguistic landscapes; multilingualism

1 Introduction

Linguistic landscapes provide us with a valuable insight into linguistic diversity, language barriers, boundaries, and the link between language use and identity. The role of language in the negotiation of power dynamics, agencies, and identities becomes particularly central in politically and socially contested areas (Themistocleous, 2020), multi-ethnic and multilingual centres, or in border zones along migrant routes (Faloppa, 2023).

This study considers borderscapes as a fluid zone of multifaceted encounters and relationships and explores them by looking at linguistic signs of migration in two areas of the French-Italian border, in particular along the mountain paths between Ventimiglia and Menton and between Clavière and Briançon. This attempt at a sociolinguistic analysis of the borderscape through a linguistic landscape (LL) approach shows its whole potential — and complexity — when confronted with the different codes and multiple human and social dynamics that exist and interact around borders (Faloppa, 2020).

2 Background

Linguistic Landscape literature has studied areas along borders, such as the border between coastal cities in France and Italy (Tufi & Blackwood, 2016), Greek and Turkish Cyprus (Themistocleous, 2019), and

between urban and rural areas of Hong Kong (Militello et al., 2023), and it has recognised the complexity of such landscapes.

In these dynamics, Linguistic Landscapes play a significant role, and their investigation can offer us an insight into language use and identity, and the language barriers and boundaries that exist alongside — but often do not coincide with — geopolitical boundaries (Landry & Bourhis, 1997). Such a study can lead to a deeper understanding of sociolinguistic stratification and multilingual interactions, exemplifying the linguistic diversity that top-down language policies and discourses may not take into account, language conflict, and cultural mediation.

Borders and border zones in relation to migration phenomena exist on a both very concrete and symbolic level, where discursively framed borders serve as a powerful narrative mechanism, and the border is seen as an imaginative place, a “process of bordering” (Vaughan-Williams, 2015, p. 6), which furthers the exclusion or — more rarely — inclusion of bodies and voices (Faloppa, 2020). Applying the concept of borderscapes, initially intended by Appudurai (Appadurai, 1996) as an area that overcomes the idea of clear-cut national territories and is instead shaped by transnational flows, to Linguistic Landscape research can provide new perspectives from a multicultural and multilingual angle, and it can challenge dynamics of othering, inclusion, and exclusion (Faloppa, 2023).

This project focuses on the signs found on the migration routes that intersect Ventimiglia (the last Italian town before the French border) and the Côte d’Azur, and that follow the mountain paths between Clavière and Briançon, in the touristic Hautes-Alps (see Appendix D). When in 2015 France unilaterally suspended the Schengen treaty to deal with the increased number of migrants crossing the Italian-French border, these areas, crucial points for migrants transiting through Italy and trying to reach Central Europe, became insurmountable barriers on the French side, but fragile and busy borderscapes in the Italian sections.

These border zones, where one could be stuck for weeks, months, waiting for the border to be reopened, became populated with signs: indexical, like the objects left on the paths; iconic, such as a map of the border sketched on a leaflet (Figure A.1); and symbolic, such as the graffiti on the pillars of a viaduct (Figure B.7) or the signboard from an activist organisation (Figure B.3). These border areas show a multilayered landscape of signs, from the top-down street signs in French and Italian, depending on which side of the border they appear on, to the bottom-up signs created by political activists, volunteer organisations, locals, and migrants. An analysis of these signs can enable researchers to explore how written public signs contribute to the creation of communities, complex identities, and a sense of belonging (Themistocleous, 2020).

3 Method

The idea for this study, and the primary source of data, resides in the photography by Luca Prestia for the project ‘Beyond the border: Migration and multilingual signs at European borderscapes’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2022). His photos appear quite logical and not over-emphatic. They try to capture details — often linguistic — that would have otherwise been left behind, and collect traces of passages, presences, and interactions.

The rest of the data used to construct the Linguistic Landscape in this study was collected through photographic stills available on the internet, from sources such as activist media and online newspapers, and from street-level images captured on Google Street View. While this approach is different from traditional LL fieldwork, the diversity of sources as a whole compensates for the partiality of the point of view in individual photos (Kitis & Milani, 2015). The data analysed makes up a diverse set of incomplete perspectives, which can offer us a panoramic view of such complex landscapes. The total dataset comprises

36 pictures: the ones captured by Luca Prestia’s lenses (Appendix A), the ones relating to the border zone of Ventimiglia (Appendix B), and those of the areas around Clavière and Briançon (Appendix C).

I will analyse the signs both quantitatively and qualitatively, distinguishing between top-down and bottom-up signs and following the taxonomy proposed by Spolsky and Cooper (1991), which classifies the signs according to the language found in each one of them and distinguishes between monolingual and multilingual signs. Moreover, by applying Scollon and Wong Scollon’s (2003) Geosemiotics framework, this project aims to go beyond quantifying the number of languages: signs can only be understood when related to their placement in a social and cultural context, and the notions of code preference, inscription, and emplacement, together with the status of the signs, can give us a deeper understanding of the relationship between a Linguistic Landscape and its socio-cultural context.

4 Analysis and Discussion

The data collected for this project comprises a mix of top-down and bottom-up signs. The top-down signs account for less than one third of the total data and, in most cases, their function for the purposes of our LL analysis is two-fold: on one hand, they show the languages chosen by the language policies of two different nations, while on the other they often consist of street signs that other agents in the landscape have written over with spray paint, and therefore serve as a medium for the different messages and languages used in bottom-up transgressive signs (Figure C.1).

The monolingual top-down signs typically include writing in French or Italian, depending on which side of the border they appear on; they usually give information to the drivers crossing the border and, when they contain multiple languages, the official language of the country they are situated in appears first, with a partial translation in the official language of the other country and in English (Figures B.10, B.11).

Bottom-up signs show a higher degree of variability in the languages used. French and English are the languages most prevalently used for graffiti, protest signs, and social and political messages. The signs created by local support organisations tend to be multilingual and, differently from the signs placed by authorities, they often include languages other than French, Italian, and English, such as Arabic. Table 1 summarises the languages found in the Linguistic Landscape and their prevalence.

Table 1: *Languages in the Linguistic Landscape of the observed areas of the French-Italian border*

Language(s) on public signs	Number	Percentage
French	17	40%
Italian	5	12%
English	7	16%
French, Italian & English	3	7.5%
French, English & Arabic	2	5%
French, Italian, English & Arabic	2	5%

French, Italian, English, Arabic & other languages	1	2.5%
No Language or unclear	5	12%
Total	43	100%

The top-down signs in this dataset are clearly not directed towards the migrants, and they do not even take into account or show their presence in the area. A sign that stands out as the only one that indirectly acknowledges the flux of migration through this border area is the one in Figure 1: it is written just in Italian and directed to the drivers on the highway, warning them of the presence of possible pedestrians. The “pedestrians” the sign refers to are the migrants that, often during the night, would try to cross the border on foot, risking and sometimes losing their lives.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a variable message sign above the entrance of a tunnel, showing the words ‘Possibili pedoni, prudenza’ [Possible pedestrians, caution] in red. This image can be found in di Blasio (2016). — Editors’ note]

Figure 1: ‘Possible pedestrians, caution’, Ventimiglia (Di Blasio, 2016).

The majority of the data comprises bottom-up signs, which will be the main focus of the rest of this study. They can be loosely classified in three different categories: the ones placed by activist organisations and volunteers to help migrants, the graffiti with socio-political messages, and the protest signs and messages left by migrants in refuge centres.

The leaflets, banners, and signboards placed by activist organisations and volunteers aim to help migrants or give information about the area and the existing refuge centres; these consist of authorized signs, such as the ones placed by the Red Cross while it was active in Ventimiglia (Figure B.1), and more often transgressive signs placed by grassroots and activist organisations that became active because of a lack of official or institutional help (Figures B.3, B.4). Figure 2 shows the sign of a self-managed refuge, and both the lexical and code choices clearly position the activist organisation who created it on the side of migrating people and opposed to right-wing politics and authority. The text is constructed in a complementary way (Reh, 2004), switching between French, Italian, and English, evoking an idea of openness, inclusivity, and an ideal absence of borders.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: two signs next to each other on the exterior of a glass window.

Left: a sign handwritten in block capitals, which reads (the slash symbol indicates a line break): ‘; Chez Jesus! / Rifugio autogestito / here nessuno is estrangere / tranne:.fasci.sbirri. passeurs.’ [Chez Jesus! / (Italian:) Self-managed refuge / (English:) here (Italian:) no one (English:) is (French:) foreign / (Italian:) apart from: fascists, cops, (French:) smugglers.]

Right: a smaller, printed sign with more text; parts that are legible from the photo, from top to bottom, all in capitals: ‘CI ACCUSANO DI SOLIDARIETÀ / SIAMO TUTTI COLPEVOLI’ [Italian: They accuse us

of solidarity, we are all guilty]; ‘SU QUEI SENTIERI C'ERAVAMO TUTTE!’ [Italian: We were all on those trails!]; and in English, ‘DEFEND SOLIDARITY / SMASH THE BORDERS’. This image can be found in “Val Susa” (2018). — Editors’ note]

Figure 2: *‘Chez Jesus! Self-managed refuge, here no one is foreign apart from: fascists, cops, smugglers’, ‘They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty! Defend solidarity, smash the border!’ signs in Clavière (“Val Susa”, 2018).*

The graffiti found on walls and abandoned buildings, on street signs, highway guard rails, and rocky mountain paths are transgressive signs probably created by activists and locals. In most cases they show social and political messages that call for no borders and freedom of movement (Figures A.9, A.10, C.3, C.4, C.5), and express the consequences of strict border control (Figure C.2); exceptions are the arrows and crosses used to show which path is more or less safe to the migrants passing through the border zone (Figures A.2, A.8). The signs collected around Clavière are often graffiti carrying social and political messages. Figure 3 poses itself as an interesting example because it shows the layering of signs: someone painted on a highway guard rail the message “no one is illegal” in Italian, then authorities tried to cover up the sign with white paint.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 15). — Editors’ note]

Figure 3: *Writing saying ‘no one is illegal’ in Clavière, covered (Photo by Luca Prestia).*

The protest signs (Figure B.13) and messages left by migrants in reception centres such as the Refuge Solidaire in Briançon (Figures A.3, A.4, A.5, A.6) are often written in French, as the language shared with the authorities that deny them access to France. A sign in English stands out (Figure 4): ‘hope’ is seen as a word that can be read and understood by as many people as possible, where the choice of code uses English as a lingua franca (Backhaus, 2006).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 21). — Editors’ note]

Figure 4: *Photo by Luca Prestia.*

The careful investigation of some bottom-up data through the Geosemiotics framework (Scollon & Wong Scollon, 2003) can help us report a sociolinguistic landscape that shows the continuous negotiation and adaptation through language by the people that pass through, live, and coexist at the border.

The Orientation map in Figure 5 represents a bridge between the borderscapes of Ventimiglia and Clavière, 200 kilometres apart from each other but united in a Linguistic Landscape with common social actors. The emplacement system of this sign is particularly significant. The map shows the sign of a long journey: it was found nearby Ventimiglia, on a mountain trail leading to France, but it was made by civil society organisations to help migrants trying to cross the border between Clavière and Haute Savoy (Faloppa, 2023). In terms of code preference, English appears first, then French, and then Arabic, and the three languages are related by a duplicating relationship (Reh, 2004).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a creased map on the ground. The title of the map is given in three languages in the upper left corner: in English, ‘Map of borders four you [sic] safety’; and, of the same meaning, in French and Arabic. To the left, a map legend is given in the same three languages. Part of the French-Italian border is shown on the map, with its majority labelled as ‘border always dangerous’, and a small section near Clavière as ‘border less dangerous’. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure 5: ‘Orientation map of border crossing points at Clavière [...] found at Ventimiglia’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).

Kesha Niya, a grassroots organisation working in Ventimiglia, primarily supports people who have been illegally denied entry into France, and the signs depicted in Figure 6, both inscribed on movable objects, are clear examples of that.

Figure 6 (a) contains overlapping text (Reh, 2004) in English, Italian, French, and Arabic, and it schematically provides information about the area migrants find themselves stuck in, a sketched map, bus times, and points of interest for medical aid and distribution of food and necessities.

Figure 6 (b) becomes very significant when examined with regard to its emplacement. In fact, it is probably one of the first signs people see when they stop at the ‘breakfast spot’ put up by Kesha Niya before trying to cross the border. The sign aims at catching the viewer’s attention to warn them about the danger of French border authorities stealing their documents, and it does so through its bright colours and illustration. The codes seem to not be organised hierarchically, the text is duplicated in Arabic, English, Italian, French, and two other languages (possibly Urdu and a language written with Aramaic script). The material used to produce the signs, cloth and tin, are more permanent than paper, but indicate less permanence than an official sign would.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2021, 4th image). — Editors’ note]

(a) Welcome sign showing a map of the area, bus, times, and necessities distribution, May 2021

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 2nd image). — Editors’ note]

(b) ‘Migrants! Police can steal your documents, make a copy, or take a picture’ sign, March 2022

Figure 6: Pictures from Kesha Niya organisation.

5 Conclusion

The sociolinguistic analysis of borderscapes tells us that there is still a lot to study and learn about the signs found along border zones. The Linguistic Landscape of two areas along the border between Italy and France, in the proximity of Ventimiglia and Clavière, presents us with a stratification of information and languages. The signs come from a variety of sources such as activists, migrants, and organisations, and are directed towards multiple viewers: the people migrating, the authorities limiting their freedom of movement, the drivers along the roads they cross, and the wider society they interact with. Recomposing the wide array of

signs and carefully analysing data through a precise framework such as the one introduced by Scollon and Wong Scollon (2003) may lend us a new way to look at these borders and at the multiple human and social dynamics shaping their Linguistic Landscape, where multilingualism is a possible means to overcome cultural boundaries.

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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix A: Beyond the Border: Migration and Multilingual Signs at European Borderscapes

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a creased map on the ground. The title of the map is given in three languages in the upper left corner: in English, ‘Map of borders four you [sic] safety’; and, of the same meaning, in French and Arabic. To the left, a map legend is given in the same three languages. Part of the French-Italian border is shown on the map, with its majority labelled as ‘border

always dangerous’, and a small section near Clavière as ‘border less dangerous’. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.1: *‘Orientation map of border crossing points at Clavière [...] found at Ventimiglia’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 17). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.2: *‘signs to alert migrants of possible dangers along the trail from Ventimiglia [...] to Menton’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 7). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.3: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 13). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.4: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 14). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.5: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 8). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.6: *‘The West kills Africa’, on a wall of the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 15). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.7: *Writing saying ‘no one is illegal’ in Clavière, covered (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found Faloppa (2020, Fig. 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.8: *Arrows to show the way, Briançon (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found Faloppa (2020, Fig. 17). — Editors' note]

Figure A.9: *Graffiti on an abandoned building in Briançon, 'no borders' (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 9). — Editors' note]

Figure A.10: *Graffiti along the road leading to France nearby Clavière, 'there are no borders', July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 18). — Editors' note]

Figure A.11: *'An informal check point set up by the French border patrol on the hills above the city of Menton' (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 21). — Editors' note]

Figure A.12: *'The "Hope" sign, and colourful knots left by migrants on the fence at the Italian-French border at 'Hill of the dead' (Italy), July 2017' (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020; photo by Luca Prestia).*

8.2 Appendix B: Pictures from Ventimiglia and Menton

[Image not included due to Google's restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: Exterior of a windowed, one-story building, with various pieces of graffiti on the visible wall:

https://www.google.com/maps/@43.8170809,7.5893452,3a,90y,233.03h,80.89t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sJlgPMpAPIIFH_XsTkdBn_Q!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D9.11%26panoid%3DJlgPMpAPIIFH_XsTkdBn_Q%26yaw%3D233.03!7i16384!8i8192?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MTAwMS4wIKXMDS0ASAFQAw%3D%3D — Editors' note]

Figure B.1: *Abandoned building where Campo Roja used to be. Google Streetview 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Della Croce (2017, cover photo). — Editors' note]

Figure B.2: *Notice of closure of the reception centre for families in Sant'Antonio alle Gianchette (Della Croce, 2017).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Niya (2018, 5th image). — Editors' note]

Figure B.3: *Breakfast at the Kesha Nyia organisation (Kesha Nyia, 2018).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 4th image).
— Editors’ note]

Figure B.4: *Welcome sign from Kesha Nyia organisation (Kesha Nyia, 2021).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 2nd image).
— Editors’ note]

Figure B.5: *‘Migrants! Police can steal your documents, make a copy or take a picture’ sign (Kesha Nyia, 2022).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2019, 2nd image).
— Editors’ note]

Figure B.6: *Modified date of birth on refusal of entry (Kesha Nyia, 2019).*

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: View of the shaded space beneath a viaduct. Various piece of graffiti can be seen on the base of the supporting pillars:
<https://www.google.com/maps/@43.8008418,7.5955398,3a,75y,81.31h,84.84t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sfMB_6WV_uEHBkypfZe7_2A!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D5.15999999999997%26panoid%3DFMB_6WV_uEHBkypfZe7_2A%26yaw%3D81.31!7i16384!8i8192?entry=ttu&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MTAwMS4wIKXMDS0ASAFAw%3D%3D> — Editors’ note]

Figure B.7: *Viaduct used as shelter. Google Streetview, November 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a variable message sign above the entrance of a tunnel, showing the words ‘Possibili pedoni, prudenza’ [Possible pedestrians, caution] in red. This image can be found in di Blasio (2016). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.8: *‘Possible pedestrians, caution’, Ventimiglia (di Blasio, 2016).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Alfano (2023). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.9: *‘Open the border’ on a rock in front of the French border control (Alfano, 2023).*

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: View on a highway. On the side of the highway is a sign with blue background and white lettering that reads: ‘Bienvenue / L’autoroute est à vous / Bevenuti / Welcome’ [(French:) Welcome / The highway is yours / (Italian:) Welcome / (English:) Welcome]:
<<https://www.google.com/maps/@43.7895122,7.5258047,3a,75y,303.74h,75.95t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sBY01-FgbF61cgwqGE4eBBg!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels->

Figure C.3: *'Life doesn't need papers' written on a wall in Clavière. Google Streetview, November 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Dumont (2018, last image). — Editors' note]

Figure C.4: *'Ain't no mountain high enough! Migration is liberty' written on a wall in Clavière (Dumont, 2018).*

[Image not included due to Google's restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: Three messages spray-painted on a wall in block capitals, presumably all by different hands. In red: 'Nous danserons sur vos centres de rétention' [We will dance on your detention centres]. On top of the previous message, in black: 'Mort aux fachos' [Death to the fascists]. To the left of the previous message, in white: 'a' and 'anti-', positioned in such a manner that when combined with the message in black it reads 'A mort aux anti-fachos' [To death to the anti-fascists]. — Editors' note]

Figure C.5: *Graffiti in Clavière: 'We will dance on your detention centres', 'death to the fascists', 'to death to the anti-fascists'. Google Streetview, November 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Dubale (2022, 1st image, not counting the cover photo). — Editors' note]

Figure C.6: *'Freedom of movement!' graffiti in an abandoned building in France (Dubale, 2022).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: two signs next to each other on the exterior of a glass window.

Left: a sign handwritten in block capitals, which reads (the slash symbol indicates a line break): '¡Chez Jesus! / Rifugio autogestito / here nessuno is etrangere / tranne:.fasci.sbirri. passeurs.' [Chez Jesus! / (Italian:) Self-managed refuge / (English:) here (Italian:) no one (English:) is (French:) foreign / (Italian:) apart from: fascists, cops, (French:) smugglers.]

Right: a smaller, printed sign with more text; parts that are legible from the photo, from top to bottom, all in capitals: 'CI ACCUSANO DI SOLIDARIETÀ / SIAMO TUTTI COLPEVOLI' [Italian: They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty]; 'SU QUEI SENTIERI C'ERAVAMO TUTTE!' [Italian: We were all on those trails!]; and in English, 'DEFEND SOLIDARITY / SMASH THE BORDERS'. This image can be found in "Val Susa" (2018). — Editors' note]

Figure C.7: *'Chez Jesus! Self-managed refuge, here no one is foreign apart from: fascists, cops, smugglers', 'They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty! Defend solidarity, smash the border!' signs in Clavière ("Val Susa", 2018).*

8.4 Appendix D: Maps of the Border

Figure D.1: Way from Ventimiglia to Menton. Google Maps, November 2023.

Figure D.2: Way from Clavière to Briançon. Google Maps, November 2023.